

METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS IN THE CONTEXT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract: At the present stage of the development of education in the world and domestic pedagogy are increasingly turning to the idea of inclusive education, which implies access to education for all, including for persons with special educational needs. Supporting the idea of inclusive education, implementing the introduction of inclusive practice, educational institutions operate in an innovative mode. The professional standard of teachers indicates that in the new social conditions there is a requirement – the willingness and ability of teachers to teach all persons without exception, regardless of their inclinations, development abilities, limited opportunities. This requirement entails the expansion of the functional responsibilities of teachers, changes in professionally significant and personal characteristics, but reliance only on traditional pedagogical skills and abilities is insufficient. The presentation of new functions and the increase in the requirements for the activities of teachers in the context of inclusive education lead to various difficulties for them. Practice of educational organizations higher education in the field of teaching people with special educational needs indicates that the educational process requires deep study, especially the content of its educational and methodological support, which significantly complicates the process of implementing inclusive education technologies. It is necessary to develop scientific and methodological complexes, methodological and educational products, programs professional training of teachers to work in inclusive education.

Keywords: information competence of teachers, special education, higher inclusive education, domestic pedagogy, persons with special educational needs, traditional pedagogical skill, inclusive educational technology

INTRODUCTION:

The global pedagogical system is increasingly focusing on the idea of inclusive education, which is a proven and effective way to develop international education in the world, which is for everyone, including people with special educational needs, speakers of minority languages too, provides with equal learning opportunities. In addition, in an inclusive education system, all children are educated in the same classes, in the same schools.

The World Conference on Education for All was held in Jomtien, Thailand. As a result of the conference, the World Declaration on EFA was adopted, in which representatives of more than one hundred and fifty states, as well as international and non-governmental organizations approved the status of education as one of the fundamental human rights by other legislative acts, it is too early to talk about the readiness of universities to implement the practice of inclusive education. University practice shows that the creation of a methodological system in a university can be individual and collective. At the same time, methodological competence can be learned in the teaching staff, be the result of their common harmony and agreement, since the teaching staff of the university develops and implements individual methodological tools and technologies, and in the process of collective work of departments and teaching units of universities, a strategy and tactics for organizing methodological work of the university are being developed, forms and means of methodological work are being improved, teacher training (in the process of educational and methodological, scientific-methodical, organizational-methodical, expert methodical work). Clarification of the content and technologies of methodological work in the conditions of inclusive education takes place by taking into account medical, social and professional organizational requirements, limitations and opportunities.

The study of integration problems, including integration in education, is attributed to the priority areas of social and pedagogical research in different countries of the world. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that professional higher education should be equally accessible to everyone, based on everyone's abilities and aimed at the full development of the individual. 2015 by the UN General Assembly as a "plan to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all". These goals were named in the resolution of the General Assembly "Agenda for the period up to 2030" and they replaced the Millennium Development Goals. This right to education is enshrined in the Constitutions of many States. Positive changes are currently taking place in education systems, but at the same time, the realization of the rights of persons with disabilities to receive higher education is associated with a number of obstacles that are not so much economic and medical as psychological and pedagogical in nature, related to the tolerant attitude of society to the very problem of obtaining higher education by disabled people. Professional educational organizations and educational organizations of higher education, as well as organizations, special conditions for students with disabilities to receive education should be created

by those who carry out educational activities in the main vocational training programs.

Special conditions for education for students with disabilities - conditions for training, education and development of such students, including: the use of special computer programs and teaching methods, special textbooks and didactic materials, technical training tools, group and individual remedial classes; ensuring access to the buildings of organizations engaged in educational activities and other conditions, without which it is impossible or difficult for students with disabilities to master educational programs.

The active development of the market economy, growing competition in the labor market and the introduction of new educational standards are constantly tightening the requirements for the level of professional readiness of future specialists. It is especially difficult for people with disabilities and disabilities to meet this level. However, traditional vocational training does not always effectively solve these tasks. Insufficient research on the professional and informational competence of teachers, as well as the socio-professional adaptation of students with disabilities in relation to the conditions of inclusive higher education necessitates a special scientific understanding of this problem in the aspect of our research.

At the level of the state policy "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", the republic provides for the active participation of persons with disabilities in the social life of the country. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated 28.01.2022 establishes the priority of further improvement of the system of social adaptation of persons with disabilities and their correctional and pedagogical assistance. There have been positive changes in our republic related to both scientific and practical achievements in the field of medicine and special education. Technological modernization of higher education is being carried out, based on the widespread use of information technologies.

MAIN PART:

New phenomena in the field of education and upbringing reflect the corresponding socio-economic changes and are conditioned by cultural and historical patterns of development of society. The whole process of human activity takes place in a certain socio-cultural environment, developing on the basis of national historical and cultural experience, economic and political situation, determining the formation and development of personality.

The current stage in the development of Russian society is characterized by the processes of socio-economic stabilization, which create favorable conditions for the transition from the declarative proclamation of humanistic ideas and goals of social development to their real implementation in the social sphere. One of the defining directions of these social transformations, of course, is the integration of people with disabilities into society. Integration is based mainly on the adoption of two different differentiated ways of life and education – for normal and special people. The special significance of this direction is due to the fact that almost all categories of people with disabilities in our country have lived in conditions of segregation for many decades (from the Latin segregation “separation”). As a result, today, in addition to solving many complex regulatory, organizational, and technical problems, it is necessary to overcome numerous negative socio-psychological consequences of such isolation, complicating the processes of mutual adaptation of society and people with disabilities.

Under the influence of the ideas of integration and tolerance in modern conditions in the field of domestic education, the search for new conceptual solutions that contribute to the harmonization of human relations in general and the adaptation of people with special educational needs (OOP) by ensuring the accessibility of a common educational space for them is also intensified. The integration of personality into a common space and the creation of “equal opportunities” through interaction with people around can help people with OOP to get a quality education and find themselves in life. From this point of view, educational inclusion (from the English inclusive “inclusive”), built on a new relationship between the individual, society and the state, is recognized as the most humane and becomes one of the main priorities. This requires the creation and maintenance of such an inclusive educational model that would take into account successful international developments and the specifics of Russian reality, would implement a social order to ensure inclusive education at all levels of the system, in particular, within higher education.

These search directions are accompanied by the identification of the inclusive orientation of higher education as a new stage in its development, systemic innovation and even as a factor of its modernization, as a result of which not only a space, an environment, but also an integral system of such inclusion is created.

In this regard, scientists are discussing the specifics of an inclusive educational model reflecting psychological, pedagogical, legal and social aspects (I.B. Agaeva, O.A. Denisova, I.N.Egorov, V.Z. Kantor, N.A. Korostyleva, O.L. Lekhanova, V.I.

Lubovsky, N.N.Malofeev, A.A. Panfilov, V.G. Sukhykh, I.F. Filchenkova, T.V. Furyaeva, etc.); its state, taking into account the problems, mainly barriers and risks of its implementation (A.P.Avdeeva, L.M. Volosnikova, G. Z. Efimova, O.V. Ogorodnova, Yu.S. Rinchinova, Yu.A.Safonova, E. Yu. Shinkareva), ways to resolve them and prospects for further development of inclusive education (S.N. Kashtanova, F.D. Rasskazov). An inclusive educational model should be conceptually grounded, that is, contain a refined conceptual apparatus, include proven methodological forms of implementation that allow not only to meet the needs and develop the capabilities of people with OOP, but also to realize a productive level of readiness for inclusive education of teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Computer technologies act as a means of forming (organizing and managing) educational activities, setting and solving educational tasks, performing professional actions in the full composition of their components. A computer can be considered as a specific means of modeling educational activity, which is capable of acting in several fundamental functions – as a means of modeling the subject content of objects of assimilation; as a means of modeling the appropriate methods of action; as a means of modeling interactions and organizing joint activities (“student – group of students”; “student – teacher”, “student – group of students – teacher” as a means of implementing forms of control and evaluation of students' actions adequate to the structure of activity and content of objects of assimilation.

Next, we conducted a comparative analysis of the results of the work on the practical implementation of pedagogical conditions by comparing the data of the initial, intermediate and control sections made in experimental and control groups.

Motivational criterion

Figure 1– Distribution of teachers of the control and experimental groups according to the content criterion on an intermediate slice

CONCLUSION:

The conducted theoretical and experimental research allowed us to make the following generalizations and brief conclusions:

Inclusive education is currently one of the strategically important directions of the development of domestic education. A particularly important role in its implementation is played by higher educational institutions that provide conditions for the full-fledged social integration of a large category of people with OOP, their personal and professional self-determination. To form an optimal inclusive model, a teacher with a high level of professional, including methodological competence in the field of designing educational space and educational products, ready for dynamic changes in the educational process, is needed.

In this regard, the creation of professional training of teachers for work in inclusive education is in demand in the domestic higher school.

The process of developing methodological competence is a model that can function successfully under the following pedagogical conditions: active involvement of teachers in the implementation of the network interaction of an inclusive educational environment, the development of an educational and methodological complex, providing step-by-step methodological support of the teacher through the developed individual development program.

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